

Sintering behavior of the sol-gel derived aluminium titanate precursor

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Aluminium titanate has been prepared by following sol-gel technique. The densification of the noncrystalline precursor powder is significantly influenced by the oxide and non-oxide additives. The additives affect the stability and anisotropic thermal expansion of aluminium titanate as reflected through measurement of the thermomechanical properties of the sintered product.

Aluminium titanate was first considered to be refractory material in 1950 because of its high melting point and a low bulk thermal expansion. In recent years, attention has been particularly focussed on its application in combustion engines as insulation for exhaust port and as positive component in the catalytic converter. Various approaches have been made for the preparation of aluminium titanate in various routes¹. Buscagila and Battilana² found the decomposition of $Al_{1-x}Mg_xTi_{1+x}O_5$ solid solution in the temperature range 900–1175°, and observed that the transformation is kinetically hindered at lower temperature. The sintering behavior, grain growth and microstructural features were studied by Mani *et al.*³. The volume expansion due to the aluminium titanate formation in the voids of the skeletal structure and densification progressed through grain growth⁴. The hysteric effects during thermal cycling was observed by Perera and Carsidy⁵. High density composites with controlled microstructure having high fracture toughness was produced by Runyan and Bennison⁶. The improvement of thermomechanical properties by incorporation of ZrO₂ was found to be related to the polymorphic transformation of ZrO₂⁷.

Present investigation was undertaken to generate precursor powder of aluminium titanate through sol-gel process in inorganic system and subsequent densification in presence of refractory additives.

Results and Discussion

The physicochemical characteristics of the synthetic hydrogel are : TiO₂, 36.50%; Al₂O₃, 36.45%, H₂O, 26.25%; molar ratio Al₂O₃ : TiO₂, 1 : 1; DTGA peak temp., 100, 300°; surface area, 180 m²/g; powder density, 0.612 g/cm³. Chemical analysis indicated complete interaction of the ingredient solutions. The ratio of Al₂O₃ : TiO₂ remained identical and moreover, purity of the hydrogel was also ascertained.

The thermal history of the precursor powder appears to be the main pathway to study sintering. For this purpose differential thermogravimetric analysis was performed upto 800°. Two distinct peaks were observed at 100 and 300°, the first peak corresponding to the removal of loosely bound gel water retained in the capillaries and the second peak associated with the dehydroxylation of both the oxides.

The primary effect of sintering precursor powder derived from hydrogel is manifested in shrinkage, which occurs due to particle shrinkage during expulsion of water followed by material transport. Substantial shrinkage occurred and it was found to be a temperature function upto 1300° and the shrinkage rate was significantly high, except the ZrO₂ containing bodies. In all other cases, expansion was observed at 1350°. This might be due to generation of some low melting phase. Reduction of volume occurred in the final stage due to crystallization of the amorphous phase of the original precursor powder. Continuous increase of shrinkage was observed only with ZrO₂ additive where in all other cases maximum shrinkage at 1300° occurred followed by slight expansion. All the additives reduced the shrinkage to a significant extent. Minimum shrinkage was exhibited by 5% SiC additive.

The densification behavior of a sintered compact is also characterized by a change of bulk density. The bulk density vs temperature curves reveal that maximum densification occurred at 1300° and highest bulk density was achieved by the sample without additive. The addition of carbide and the nitride phase made matrix more open. In case of ZrO₂ and Si₃N₄, the bulk density curves flattened with slight increase whereas in the other case desintering occurred. This might be due to the fact that the expansion of large pores is greater than the shrinkage of the small pores.

The porosity vs temperature relationship is shown in Fig. 1. Initially at 1250° the specimens were sufficiently porous both in presence and in absence of additives. But

Fig. 1. Relationship between apparent porosity and sintering temperature.

the porosity decreased continuously with temperature and even at 1350° the porosity reduced to 20%. The additive played a negative role in the reduction of porosity which appears to be due to their more refractory nature and due to nonformation of any eutectic with the component of the matrix. The rate of reduction was minimum with SiC additive showing higher porosity.

The results of true density measurements show that true density is a negative function of temperature in all the cases. This might be due to the formation of relatively low density Al_2TiO_5 from high density ingredients. Material with ZrO_2 additive (Batch II) exhibited the highest densities at all temperatures of sintering which could be related to the density of ZrO_2 in all polymorphic forms. Except ZrO_2 , in all other cases, the rate of decrease was slow from 1300° whereas reverse nature was observed with ZrO_2 containing sample, indicating that the rate of formation of Al_2TiO_5 was related initially due to the presence of ZrO_2 . The true density of Al_2TiO_5 is 3.56, whereas that of rutile is 4.23 and corundum 3.95 g/cm^3 , ZrO_2 containing samples exhibited highest densities due to high density of ZrO_2 in all polymorphic forms.

The importance of mechanical strength of a ceramic material is crucial considering its application in adverse condition. Due to formation and proper interlocking maximum residual flexural strength was achieved at 1300° (Fig. 2) following which the strength decreased which might be associated with the partial decomposition of the titanate phase. At 1300° maximum strength was achieved with the ZrO_2 containing samples (Table 1) and the curves follow the same sequence.

The precursor powder was completely amorphous in nature, which was evident from the absence of any peak in the X-ray diffraction pattern. The XRD patterns of the samples

Fig. 2. Relationship between flexural strength and sintering temperature.

fired at 1350° revealed the major crystalline phases as aluminium titanate along with the small amount of corundum. ZrO_2 containing samples exhibited presence of tetragonal ZrO_2 .

Table 1. Residual flexural strength (kg/cm^2) after 7th spalling cycle with the samples sintered at 1300°

Batch no.	Composition	Residual flexural strength (kg/cm^2)
I	Calcined precursor (CP)	2050
II	CP + 5% ZrO_2	1960
III	CP + 5% SiC	1502
IV	CP + 5% Si_3N_4	1408

Scanning electron microscopy of the fractured surface was performed with the samples with no additive and that containing ZrO_2 additive at 1300°. In all cases proper grain growth of aluminium titanate was observed. Grain boundary was sharp and it was evident that ZrO_2 did not play any role in the growth of titanate. Both intergranular and intragranular ZrO_2 was observed.

Conclusion: Aluminium titanate without additive indicated sufficient grain growth with proper interlocking. The microstructure was homogeneous with more or less sharp grain boundary. With the incorporation of ZrO_2 the grain size of aluminium titanate was significantly reduced and the grain boundary became more diffused. But the overall uniformity of titanate was retained. SiC incorporation made the microstructure more segregated and grain clustering was observed. The porosity as well as SiC distribution was heterogeneous in character. SiC grains appeared to be finer in nature. It is important to note that during sintering in presence of SiC in oxidizing atmosphere, there was possibility of formation of SiO_2 , which might lead to offer glassy phase. This glass might be responsible for the segregated micro-

structure. In contrast, Si_3N_4 added aluminium titanate offered stable and homogeneous microstructure with minimum residual porosity. The pores were mostly rounded or subrounded. The grain size of the titanate phase was more or less uniform. Finer grains of Si_3N_4 were also visible in the intergranular position. It should be noted that incoherence of the microstructure was achieved due to resistance offered by Si_3N_4 towards oxidation.

Thus the role of additives was seen quite prominent. The decreasing order of effectiveness of additives may be represented as $\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4 > \text{SiC} > \text{ZrO}_2 >$ without additive. This clearly indicates that properly interlocked microstructure with uniform distribution of the additives strengthens the matrix.

Experimental

The mixed hydroxide hydrogel of Al^{III} and Ti^{IV} was synthesized by the wet interaction of nonhydrolysable salts like aluminium nitrate and potassium titanate oxalate. The salt concentration was adjusted at 5% (w/w) and the pH of gel formation was 9. The hydrogel after aging was processed to remove the water-soluble impurities, dried at 60° and finally ground and milled to fine particle size.

The precursor powder was characterized by standard method of testing. The precursor powder was mixed with 5% (w/w) additives which include both oxides (ZrO_2) and non-oxide compounds (SiC , Si_3N_4). It was mixed at first by solid state mixing process, followed by dispersion in acetone with shaking. Then the solvent was evaporated. The additives were taken in very fine state of subdivision. Mainly

pellets and bars were fabricated which exhibited uniform texture and possessed sufficient strength. Sintering of the consolidated mass in the form of discs and bars was performed in muffle furnace in the normal oxidizing atmosphere. The rate of heating was $10^\circ/\text{min}$, upto 1000° followed by $5^\circ/\text{min}$ upto final temperature of heat treatment for a fixed soaking period of 2 h.

Properties of the sintered compacts were performed in the usual manner. Thermal expansion was measured by a Bahr 804 dilatometer. X-Ray diffraction was carried out using a Philips PW(1970) diffractometer. The scanning electron microscopy was done with a Hitachi S415A microscope.

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